

Implementation of Deteriorized Chemical Reagents Supply Control Using the Economic Order Quantity Method at PT. ABC

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Abstract

PT. ABC is one of the companies engaged in pharmaceuticals, more precisely in the manufacture of drugs, both tablets, caplets, capsules, syrup, ovules, injections and so on. Optimal control of raw material supplies is very important for the company so that the production process can run properly. The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method is a basic method of inventory control by finding the minimum point between the ordering fee and the storage fee. The purpose of this study is to find out the control of the inventory of some raw materials in PT. ABC uses the EOQ method. Surveys and observations with a quantitative descriptive approach are the methods used in this study. Data analysis uses the calculation formula EOQ and total inventory cost. The results showed that the application of the EOQ method in the control of raw material supplies is an emphasis on inventory costs in PT. ABC. The efficiency of the number of raw material orders each time the order, as well as the number of safety supplies can be known.

Keywords: *Supplies Deteriorized using the EOQ Method, Inventory Control Method EOQ Deteriorization.*

INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry is one type of industry that continues to grow rapidly, with an ever-growing market reach. The pharmaceutical industry in Indonesia continues to grow every year, along with the development of increasingly sophisticated Science and Technology. PT. ABC is a pharmaceutical company. The industry produces both OTC (Over the Counter) and generic (generic) medicines. The Quality Control Department is tasked with conducting a series of routine testing processes, namely conducting chemical analysis to determine the quality of the drug. Pharmaceutical products can be identified by testing in a chemical laboratory. Testing in a quality control chemistry laboratory is one of the testing of finished drugs. To do the test requires a series of analyses that require several supporting chemical reagents. Each stage of testing analysis cannot be separated from the use of chemical reagents, and there are often problems related to the unavailability of chemical reagents for the analysis process that cause delays in product production.

Table 1 Percentage Data Lead Time Product Release

Month	A number of product samples			Achievement Percentage
	Arrival	Complete	Pending	
January	634	509	125	80.3%
February	899	754	145	83.9%
March	746	654	92	87.7%
April	889	856	33	96.3%
May	715	687	28	96.1%
June	848	788	60	92.9%
July	814	798	16	98.0%
Agust	917	854	63	93.1%
Average	807.75	737.5	70.25	91.3%

Source: PT ABC QC Document (2021)

In January, February, and March, there are delays in product spending, while from April to December, there is no delay in product spending. This is due to chemical reagents being out of stock. Checking this chemical reagent is done at the end of the year, so when there is an expired or damaged reagent, it must wait for the next reagent order. The availability of chemical reagents in the field becomes one of the critical points in the product production process because chemical reagents can be likened to fuel in an analysis process, where when chemical reagents are not available in the field, the analysis process cannot be done at all, which will ultimately hamper the product production process. With problems in PT. ABC companies need to have a reagent inventory planning system that takes into account shelf life.

This research was conducted to control the supply of chemical reagents in the QC laboratory of PT. ABC to avoid the occurrence of a shortage of chemical reagent stock, also to estimate and determine the cost of chemical reagent inventory in the QC laboratory of PT. ABC, and also to determine the effectiveness of chemical reagents during storage and use and determine the reagents that occupy the highest priority in use during the process of testing in the QC laboratory of PT. ABC.

In *perishable inventory* models, daily demand is unknown but is assumed to follow a known probability distribution. Suppose y is the number of newspapers purchased and D requests. There are two penalties: overage (ordering too much) and underage (ordering too little). Pay attention to the inventory model that is easily damaged. The penalty for ordering too much is a future penalty for being outdated, at γ per unit, and the penalty for ordering too little is a penalty fee for excess demand, at p per unit.

METHODS

The type of research used is applied research, which is a process of collecting, recording, and analyzing data that is systematic and objective to help in business decision making (Williamson, 2002). Applied research serves to find solutions to specific problems. The main purpose is problem solving so that research results can be used for the benefit of either individuals or groups, or for industrial or political purposes, and not for scientific insight alone.

The EOQ method is a method used to determine the number of purchases of raw materials for each order at the lowest cost. Hansen et al. (2001) describe the relationship between EOQ as a traditional inventory management method and the associated inventory costs in it. Because the EOQ method can be used to determine the number of items to be ordered so that demand projections can be fulfilled, the objective function of this EOQ method is to minimize inventory costs (Fahmi, 2012). If the purchase of raw material inventory from outside is not from within the company, then all costs are included in the ordering costs and the costs incurred by the company as a form of maintenance in storing inventory are carrying costs. The basic concept of calculating EOQ is simple logic: the more frequent orders, the smaller the average inventory will be. This is directly proportional to the storage cost and indirectly proportional to the ordering costs, which will increase (Prabawa et al., 2019).

Safety stock, or commonly called "safety stock," is used by companies to reduce the risk of shortages and delays in receiving raw materials (Sutrisna et al., 2021). If inventory is not known with certainty, the third category of inventory costs is called "stock-out costs." Inventory shortage costs are costs that arise from not having a product when there is a demand from the customer. For example, lost sales, expedition costs (increased transportation costs, overtime hours, etc.), and the costs of interrupted production activities are examples of lost sales.

Observations were made on the pharmaceutical company PT. ABC as one of the leading pharmaceutical companies in Indonesia and Southeast Asia. Pharmaceutical company PT. ABC is located in Bekasi Regency, West Java. Time The research was conducted in 2021. The data used in this study includes secondary data, which is data that was first collected and reported by the inventory staff. In this case, the data was obtained from the documents of PT. ABC and supporting books, journals, papers, and other data. Secondary data used includes purchase data, storage costs, ordering costs, and lead time for ordering chemical reagents.

The data collection methods used in the preparation of this study are as follows:

1. Literature Studies
Looking for reference theories relevant to cases or problems found to contain data related to the topics raised in the research. This literature study is obtained from various sources, either in the form of journals, books, the internet, or guidance from the pharmacopoeia as a basis of reference in pharmaceutical companies.
2. Observation
Make a series of observations directly on the object of the problem, then collect the data from the observations and in the process of the data. Interviews were conducted to obtain data on chemical reagent purchases.
3. Documentation
Look for documents or data in the company that are considered important to be applied in research. The document is related to previous costs associated with chemical reagents, both in use and maintenance.

Instruments as a tool in using data collection methods are guidelines from observation results that in the implementation of observations are carried out directly on other instrument problem objects, namely documentation, to find documents or data in companies that are considered important to be applied in research.

Research procedures are carried out systematically so that they are easy to understand. Furthermore, the research procedure will serve as a guide in the research process.

1. **Topic Selection and Literature Analysis**
Determine this topic to determine what topics to cover in research, and Literature Studies is the process of studying theories, data, and methods related to the topic of the problem to be discussed. The study of literature in this study is taken from books, journals, and the internet to support the understanding and completeness of the data used in this study.
2. **Identify the Problem**
This stage is to get an idea of the events that are the problems that will be studied in this study and to find solutions to the problems that occur.
3. **Determination of Research Objectives**
The purpose of the research can be determined after finding a topic and conducting a Literature Study, then Identifying the problem.
4. **Data Collection**
Data collection is done by collecting historical data on the demand and use of chemical reagents in the QC Laboratory over the past 12 months.
5. **Data Processing**
Data processing is done by classifying reagents in the ABC class and calculating the cost of purchase by the EOQ deterioration method. Here are the steps from the ABC analysis:
 - a. Calculating the supply amount and exterminating
 - b. Calculate the purchase price
 - c. Calculate the percentage of cost uptake
 - d. Sort into ABC categories.Here are the steps in the data processing process:
 - a. Calculate the number of bookings
 - b. Calculate the booking period
 - c. Calculate the total cost of the purchase
 - d. Do a comparison to determine the most optimal method to ensure there is no chemical reagent damage and save total inventory.
6. **Analysis**
Analyze the data processing results to determine the best methods for reagent ordering and control.
7. **Conclusions and Suggestions**
Based on the analysis conducted, the author can write the conclusions of the results of this study. The author will also offer advice that the company can use when developing policies or making decisions about chemical reagent inventory control.

Figure 1 Flowchart Research

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data collection at PT. ABC identified the problem of the destruction of chemical reagents. Thus, the waste disposal of chemical reagents in PT. ABC became ineffective in the analisa process. Based on table 2, you can see the condition of the destruction of chemical reagents in the laboratory quality control (QC).

Table 2 List of Chemical Reagents Purchased and Disposed of at PT. ABC

No	Reagent Name	Stock	Removal	Unit Price	Total Purchase Price	Wasted Price	Brand	Suplier
1	Nitric Acid	67	7	Rp 1.863.160,00	Rp 124.831.720,00	Rp 13.042.120,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
2	Heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt	38	8	Rp 990.000,00	Rp 37.620.000,00	Rp 7.920.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
3	Ortho-phosphoric acid 85%	17	1	Rp 1.475.000,00	Rp 25.075.000,00	Rp 1.475.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
4	Ammonium Carbamate	7	1	Rp 1.944.000,00	Rp 13.608.000,00	Rp 1.944.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
5	Citric Acid Monohydrate	10	2	Rp 906.500,00	Rp 9.065.000,00	Rp 1.813.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
6	Hydrogen Peroxide 30%	6	2	Rp 1.127.000,00	Rp 6.762.000,00	Rp 2.254.000,00	Fisher	PRAGLAS RAYA
7	Oxalic Acid	5	1	Rp 1.134.000,00	Rp 5.670.000,00	Rp 1.134.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
8	Sodium Chloride	4	1	Rp 1.250.000,00	Rp 5.000.000,00	Rp 1.250.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
9	Sodium Thiosulfate Pentahydrate	5	3	Rp 473.500,00	Rp 2.367.500,00	Rp 1.420.500,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
10	Potassium Chloride	5	2	Rp 334.000,00	Rp 1.670.000,00	Rp 668.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
11	Ferroin Indikator	4	1	Rp 598.000,00	Rp 2.392.000,00	Rp 598.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
12	Tetra n-Butylammonium Hydroxide	7	2	Rp 5.319.000,00	Rp 37.233.000,00	Rp 10.638.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA
13	Mercury II Chloride	16	4	Rp 2.715.000,00	Rp 43.440.000,00	Rp 10.860.000,00	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA

(Source: Internal Company)

Reagent needs are used for analytical needs in the QC Laboratory PT. ABC is deterministic, or known for sure. In this case, it aims to determine the optimal order quantity and optimal order frequency so that there is no more destruction of reagents that results in waste in Table 2. Therefore the author does the classification of data presented in Table 3 to find out the priority level and the exact quantity of purchases

The classification of ABC obtained the result that there needs to be a concern for the quantity of purchases so that there is no deterrence, namely class A, which includes Reagents like Nitric Acid with a total of 7 bottles of extermination, Mercury III Chloride with a total of 4 bottles, Heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt with a total of 8 bottles, and Tetra n-Butylammonium Hydroxide with a total of 2 bottles.

Table 3 ABC Classification

No	Reagent Name	Brand	Suplier	Stock	Removal	Unit Price	Total Purchase Price	Wasted Price	%Buy Cumulative	%Absorb	%Cumulative	Class
1	Nitric Acid	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	67	7	Rp 1.863.160,00	Rp 124.831.720,00	Rp 13.042.120,00	Rp 124.831.720,00	39,663	39,663	A
2	Mercury II Chloride	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	16	4	Rp 2.715.000,00	Rp 43.440.000,00	Rp 10.860.000,00	Rp 168.271.720,00	13,802	53,465	
3	Heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	38	8	Rp 990.000,00	Rp 37.620.000,00	Rp 7.920.000,00	Rp 205.891.720,00	11,953	65,418	
4	Tetra n-Butylammonium Hydroxide	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	7	2	Rp 5.319.000,00	Rp 37.233.000,00	Rp 10.638.000,00	Rp 243.124.720,00	11,830	77,248	
5	Ortho-phosphoric acid 85%	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	17	1	Rp 1.475.000,00	Rp 25.075.000,00	Rp 1.475.000,00	Rp 268.199.720,00	7,967	85,215	B
6	Ammonium Carbamate	Fisher	PRAGLAS RAYA	7	1	Rp 1.944.000,00	Rp 13.608.000,00	Rp 1.944.000,00	Rp 281.807.720,00	4,324	89,538	
7	Citric Acid Monohydrate	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	10	2	Rp 906.500,00	Rp 9.065.000,00	Rp 1.813.000,00	Rp 290.872.720,00	2,880	92,419	
8	Hydrogen Peroxide 30%	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	6	2	Rp 1.127.000,00	Rp 6.762.000,00	Rp 2.254.000,00	Rp 297.634.720,00	2,148	94,567	C
9	Oxalic Acid	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	5	1	Rp 1.134.000,00	Rp 5.670.000,00	Rp 1.134.000,00	Rp 303.304.720,00	1,802	96,369	
10	Sodium Chloride	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	4	1	Rp 1.250.000,00	Rp 5.000.000,00	Rp 1.250.000,00	Rp 308.304.720,00	1,589	97,957	
11	Ferroin Indikator	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	4	1	Rp 598.000,00	Rp 2.392.000,00	Rp 598.000,00	Rp 310.696.720,00	0,760	98,717	
12	Sodium Thiosulfate Pentahydrate	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	5	3	Rp 473.500,00	Rp 2.367.500,00	Rp 1.420.500,00	Rp 313.064.220,00	0,752	99,469	
13	Potassium Chloride	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	5	2	Rp 334.000,00	Rp 1.670.000,00	Rp 668.000,00	Rp 314.734.220,00	0,531	100,000	
Total						Rp 20.129.160,00	Rp 314.734.220,00	Rp 55.016.620,00			100,000	

(Source :Data Processing)

Viewed in Table 3 of the ABC classification, which describes some reagents that fall into class A, this shows that the reagent is the most widely used reagent in the buying and extermination process. Decreased deterioration rates lead to decreases in the level of demand for goods and the average profit earned. This can lead to an increase in the inventory value of goods and affect optimal ordering times. If the rate of deterioration decreases, then a business must provide goods with a smaller amount to avoid the occurrence of excess goods that can affect the quantity of reagents.

Table 4 Calculation of Economic Order Quantity (EOQ)

No	Reagent Name	Stock	Removal	Unit Price	A	D	h	teta	teta.T	Q	Q(RU)	T	TC
1	Nitric Acid	67	7	Rp1.863.160,00	Rp 110.000,00	60	Rp 27.313,43	0,104	0,040	22,003	23	0,383	Rp 605.296,59
2	Mercury II Chloride	16	4	Rp2.715.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	12	Rp 114.375,00	0,250	0,104	4,854	5	0,417	Rp 560.129,92
3	Heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt	38	8	Rp 990.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	30	Rp 48.157,89	0,211	0,084	11,748	12	0,400	Rp 572.231,84
4	Tetra n-Butylammonium Hydroxide	7	2	Rp5.319.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	5	Rp 261.428,57	0,286	0,171	2,109	3	0,600	Rp 598.878,59
5	Ortho-phosphoric acid 85%	17	1	Rp1.475.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	16	Rp 107.647,06	0,059	0,022	5,729	6	0,375	Rp 618.662,23
6	Ammonium Carbamate	7	1	Rp1.944.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	6	Rp 261.428,57	0,143	0,071	2,274	3	0,500	Rp 621.648,73
7	Citric Acid Monohydrate	10	2	Rp 906.500,00	Rp 110.000,00	8	Rp 183.000,00	0,200	0,100	3,140	4	0,500	Rp 598.511,20
8	Hydrogen Peroxide 30%	6	2	Rp1.127.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	4	Rp 305.000,00	0,333	0,167	1,768	2	0,500	Rp 542.674,67
9	Oxalic Acid	5	1	Rp1.134.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	4	Rp 366.000,00	0,200	0,100	1,589	2	0,500	Rp 598.511,20
10	Sodium Chloride	4	1	Rp1.250.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	3	Rp 457.500,00	0,250	0,167	1,250	2	0,667	Rp 649.012,00
11	Feroin Indikator	4	1	Rp 598.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	3	Rp 457.500,00	0,250	0,167	1,250	2	0,667	Rp 649.012,00
12	Sodium Thiosulfate Pentahydrate	5	3	Rp 473.500,00	Rp 110.000,00	2	Rp 366.000,00	0,600	0,600	1,250	2	1,000	Rp 561.641,56
13	Potassium Chloride	5	2	Rp 334.000,00	Rp 110.000,00	3	Rp 366.000,00	0,400	0,267	1,430	2	0,667	Rp 565.823,24
Total Inventory Cost													Rp 7.742.033,78

(Source: Data Processing)

From table 4, obtained at the time of booking (T) reagent purchase using the formula (Widayana et al. 2011):

$$T = \frac{Q}{D}$$

Quantity of booking (Q) by using the formula

$$Q = \sqrt{\frac{2AD(D + \theta)}{h}}$$

Inventory total cost (TC) using the formula

$$TC = \frac{A}{T} + \frac{hD(e^{\theta T} - \theta T - 1)}{TQ^2}$$

Note:

A = Ordering cost (Rp per order)

H = Annual holding cost (Rp per unit per year)

D = Demand (in units)

θ = Deterioration rate

T = Denotes the order period (in years)

Q = Order quantity (units)

TC = Total Cost Inventory (Rp)

Based on the calculations above, the possibility of reagent waste is very small because ordering periodically with the quantity of order (Q) that has been calculated and obtained the total cost of storage and ordering as much as Rp. 7.742.033,78, after that calculates the purchase price of reagent when it has been implemented the EOQ model on PT. ABC.

Table 5 Calculation of chemical reagent purchases with the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ)

No	Reagent Name	Purchase Amount/years	Buy Total	TC	Total Cost
1	Nitric Acid	60	Rp 111.789.600,00	Rp 605.296,59	Rp 112.394.896,59
2	Mercury II Chloride	12	Rp 32.580.000,00	Rp 560.129,92	Rp 33.140.129,92
3	Heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt	30	Rp 29.700.000,00	Rp 572.231,84	Rp 30.272.231,84
4	Tetra n-Butylammonium Hydroxide	5	Rp 26.595.000,00	Rp 598.878,59	Rp 27.193.878,59
5	Ortho-phosphoric acid 85%	16	Rp 23.600.000,00	Rp 618.662,23	Rp 24.218.662,23
6	Ammonium Carbamate	6	Rp 11.664.000,00	Rp 621.648,73	Rp 12.285.648,73
7	Citric Acid Monohydrate	8	Rp 7.252.000,00	Rp 598.511,20	Rp 7.850.511,20
8	Hydrogen Peroxide 30%	4	Rp 4.508.000,00	Rp 542.674,67	Rp 5.050.674,67
9	Oxalic Acid	4	Rp 4.536.000,00	Rp 598.511,20	Rp 5.134.511,20
10	Sodium Chloride	3	Rp 3.750.000,00	Rp 649.012,00	Rp 4.399.012,00
11	Feroin Indikator	3	Rp 1.794.000,00	Rp 649.012,00	Rp 2.443.012,00
12	Sodium Thiosulfate Pentahydrate	2	Rp 947.000,00	Rp 561.641,56	Rp 1.508.641,56
13	Potassium Chloride	3	Rp 1.002.000,00	Rp 565.823,24	Rp 1.567.823,24
Total Inventory Cost					Rp267.459.633,78

(Source : Data Processing)

Table 5 Calculation of chemical reagent purchase with the economic order quantity method above can be seen with a total purchase cost of Rp. 267.459.633,78. While based on Table 3's calculation of chemical reagent purchase applied by PT. ABC can get a total cost to be incurred amounting to Rp. 314.734.220,00.

Table 6 Calculation of Chemical Reagent Purchases at PT. ABC

No	Reagent Name	Brand	Supplier	Stock	Removal	Unit Price	Total Purchase Price
1	Nitric Acid	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	67	7	Rp 1.863.160,00	Rp 124.831.720,00
2	Mercury II Chloride	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	16	4	Rp 2.715.000,00	Rp 43.440.000,00
3	Heptane-1-sulfonic acid sodium salt	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	38	8	Rp 990.000,00	Rp 37.620.000,00
4	Tetra n-Butylammonium Hydroxide	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	7	2	Rp 5.319.000,00	Rp 37.233.000,00
5	Ortho-phosphoric acid 85%	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	17	1	Rp 1.475.000,00	Rp 25.075.000,00
6	Ammonium Carbamate	Fisher	PRAGLAS RAYA	7	1	Rp 1.944.000,00	Rp 13.608.000,00
7	Citric Acid Monohydrate	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	10	2	Rp 906.500,00	Rp 9.065.000,00
8	Hydrogen Peroxide 30%	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	6	2	Rp 1.127.000,00	Rp 6.762.000,00
9	Oxalic Acid	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	5	1	Rp 1.134.000,00	Rp 5.670.000,00
10	Sodium Chloride	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	4	1	Rp 1.250.000,00	Rp 5.000.000,00
11	Ferroun Indikator	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	4	1	Rp 598.000,00	Rp 2.392.000,00
12	Sodium Thiosulfate Pentahydrate	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	5	3	Rp 473.500,00	Rp 2.367.500,00
13	Potassium Chloride	Merck	PRAGLAS RAYA	5	2	Rp 334.000,00	Rp 1.670.000,00
Total						Rp 20.129.160,00	Rp 314.734.220,00

(Source: Internal Company Data)

So by using Economic Order Quantity Method, PT ABC can save total costs that must be spent on the purchase of reagent by using the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method, with a cost savings obtained amounting to Rp 314.734.220,00 - Rp 267.459.633,78 = **Rp 47.274.586,22** or efficiency obtained by 15.02% of the results obtained before using the EOQ method. Table 7 is a comparison of the results of calculations using the EOQ method and without the use of the EOQ method.

Table 7 Comparison of Total Cost based on Company Calculations before using the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) Method and after using the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method

	Before EOQ	After EOQ	Difference
Total cost	Rp 314,734,220	Rp 267,459,634	Rp 47,274,586.22
Efficiency (%)	15.02%		

(Source: Data Processing)

Storage costs are costs related to the storage of raw materials. The details of storage costs at PT. ABC are presented on table 7. From table 7, it can be seen that the total cost after the application of the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method has a cheaper amount of value. This is because in the calculation of total cost using consideration of the number of products and minimum expiration costs and frequencies, as small as possible so that PT. ABC can minimize the total cost incurred. The total cost before applying the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method has a greater value due to PT. ABC does not take into account the number of products ordered, so the risk of an expired product is greater.

Table 8 Details of Storage Costs for 2021

Reagent		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
No.	Fee Type	Total (Rp)						
1	Electricity Cost /Month	Rp 52.500,00						
2	Handling Cost /Month	Rp 100.000,00						
Total Holding Cost		Rp 152.500,00						
		Rp 1.830.000,00						
3	Consumption Total / Years	67	16	38	7	17	7	10
Total Holding Cost		Rp 27.313,43	Rp 114.375,00	Rp 48.157,89	Rp 261.428,57	Rp 107.647,06	Rp 261.428,57	Rp 183.000,00
Reagent		8	9	10	11	12	13	
No.	Fee Type	Total (Rp)						
1	Electricity Cost /Month	Rp 52.500,00						
2	Handling Cost /Month	Rp 100.000,00						
Total Holding Cost		Rp 152.500,00						
		Rp 1.830.000,00						
3	Consumption Total / Years	6	5	4	4	5	5	
Total Holding Cost		Rp 305.000,00	Rp 366.000,00	Rp 457.500,00	Rp 457.500,00	Rp 366.000,00	Rp 366.000,00	

(Source: Data Processing)

CONCLUSION

After the data collection and processing process, it can be concluded that the availability of raw materials in PT. ABC becomes the deciding factor in the production process. Inventory control is a very important activity in a company because it can affect cost efficiency, smoothness in the production process, and the profit of PT. ABC itself.

From the results of data processing carried out by the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method, there are several reagents that have the highest number of purchases and exterminations when compared to other reagents. The highest perecation is in the class A classification, with a percentage of uptake of 77% of the existing amount. With the application of the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method, it also greatly affects the total value of purchases for companies where there is a cost saving value of Rp 47.274.586,22 or 15.02%.

In inventory models that consider deterioration levels, optimal solutions greatly influence optimal solutions. The model considers the occurrence of inventory shortages and the possibility of inventory experiencing expiration so that goods cannot be sold or used.

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